
D5.1 BUSINESS CASE IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

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Project Coordinator: Ms. **Panagiota Syropoulou,**
DRANIS SA.

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Responsible Author	Panagitois Ilias			
Contributions from	Tuna Coppens			

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List of Abbreviations

A/A	Abbreviation	Description
1	AB	Advisory Board
2	BAP	Business Cases Action Plan
3	BC	Business Case
4	BCE	Business Case Evaluators
5	BCF	Business Case Facilitator
6	BIG	Business Cases implementation Guide Lines
7	CA	Consortium Agreement
8	CBs	Certification Bodies
9	DP	Data Provider
10	EC	European Commission
11	EnU	End Users
12	EO	Earth Observation
13	EU	European Union
14	LHCs	Lighthouse Customers
15	PAs	Paying Agencies
16	PC	Project Coordinator
17	PP	Platform Provider
18	PSC	Product & Service Consumers
19	SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
20	SP	Services Provider
21	WP	Work Package
22	WPL	Work Package Leader

INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 5.1 “Business case Implementation Guidelines” is the first deliverable of WP5 led by EV ILVO. The objective of this deliverable is to provide **a common framework for project partners involved in business cases** to ensure the smooth progress of the WP5 and establish efficient communication between the different project partners and the lighthouse customers.

- In the **first section**, the general objectives, tasks and deliverables of the WP5 listed, and all **Business cases (BC)** are summarised and presented in an informative manner to help BC actors follow the vision of the Envision project declared in the grant agreement.
- The **second section**, which is the actual contribution of this deliverable, declares the actor roles, the scheduled activities within the WP and the mapping of those activities to each role. This way, we describe clearly: **which role is doing what**.
- The **third section** goes one step further: It assigns per business case the actors to the roles. This way, we describe clearly per business case: **which actor needs to do what and with whom**.

We also provide basic instructions and standard features and practices to eliminate potential communication and coordination confusion and increase efficiency. This includes communication channels, mailing lists, management of meetings (both online and physical) and monitoring and documentation guidelines (6 ANNEX).

1 General goals and objectives of WP5

ENVISION aims to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land, shifting the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific parcels and dates (or time windows) to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring.

The overall objective of WP5 is to deploy and evaluate ENVISION data products and services developed in WP3 and WP4, considering the prioritised requirements as those have been identified in WP2 (see *D2.2 Report of customer requirements from ENVISION services*).

More specifically in WP5:

- The ENVISION platform, data products and services will be **tested** under different conditions within the BC.
- The performance, usability, and effectiveness of these products and services and their impact at an economic, environmental, and societal level will be **evaluated**.
- The evaluation results will be used to **improve** the data products and services (WP3 and WP4) and support the **commercialisation and dissemination** activities of the ENVISION project (WP6, WP7).

1.1 Interrelation with other WPs

*Business cases implementation and evaluation (WP5), which is at the centre of the project work plan, will be responsible for the **planning, implementation, and evaluation of the different BCs (ENVISION products and services)** that will take place in the project.*

- The review and evaluation of existing relevant services and identifying PAs and CBs needs occur in WP2 Commercial Service Requirements. **WP5 will consider user needs identified in WP2 as a baseline for the evaluation process.**
- WP3 designs and develops the EO-enabled data products offered through the ENVISION platform while taking into consideration the end user needs identified in WP2. **The results of WP3 (data products) will be used and evaluated in WP5.** WP5 will therefore identify the needed improvements and updates in the evaluation reports, considering identified needs and priorities (WP2), and **provide them to WP3 actors in the evaluation reports**, using as baseline the WP2 user stories.
- WP4 designs and develops all aspects of the ENVISION platform. The identified end user needs of WP2 feed into WP4, and there is an exchange of information among WP2 and WP4 as the platform and ENVISION service are **co-produced** with the end-users to ensure that they are tailored to their needs. **The results of WP4 (platform and services) will be used and evaluated in WP5. WP5 will identify the needed improvements and updates in the evaluation reports, considering identified needs and priorities (WP2),** and provide them to WP4 actors.
- WP5 evaluation results will be provided to WP6 and WP7 to support the **commercialisation and dissemination activities** of the ENVISION project.

Figure 1 WP5 interactions with other WPs.

1.2 Business cases

1.2.1 Business case definition

A Business Case¹ is a sequence of actions performed in a business that produces a result of observable value to an individual actor of the business. At ENVISION, the Business Cases aim to develop innovative services able to cover specific customer needs related to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

1.2.2 Business customers and lighthouse customers definitions and level of involvement

The Business Customers are members of the consortium, and the level of involvement is defined at the Grant Agreement (GA). They are Paying Agencies (PAs) and Certification Bodies (CBs) that participate in various activities in relation to the implementation, evaluation and commercialisation of the ENVISION platform, data products and services, from the beginning of the project. They are actors at the Business Cases having the role of a customer of the business, and they act like normal "users", as potential "purchasers" and "evaluators" of the product and services.

The ENVISION **Lighthouse Customers** are not members of the consortium and are participating in ENVISION voluntarily. They face issues relative to the effective monitoring of CAP environmental requirements and agricultural certification requirements. They will test specific features of the services at a small scale.

As Lighthouse Customers have the option to choose the level and type of their involvement in the project during the beginning of ENVISION's implementation. Their contribution to the project will be significant as they will further enhance the results of ENVISION by providing extra intelligence on the users' needs and requirements and/or by participating in the (small scale) testing and evaluation of

¹ https://sceweb.uhcl.edu/helm/RationalUnifiedProcess/process/modguide/md_buc.htm

ENVISION’s services. Depending on each Lighthouse Customer’s specific needs, they will decide which ENVISION products and services they are interested in.

1.2.3 Existing business cases

As presented in Tables 1 through 4 various BCs will take place within the WP5. In each BC, the ENVISION platform, data products and services will be tested under different conditions (for example, on small scale) by the end-users (the PAs and CBs, which are project partners and act as customers) and by the lighthouse customers.

<i>Flemish Business Case: Monitoring the condition of the soil</i>		
<i>Business Customer: LV Flanders (BE)</i>		
<i>Type of organisation: Paying Agency (PA)</i>		
<i>Data products and service providers: EV ILVO</i>		
<p><i>Short description:</i> Flanders business case focuses on deploying ENVISION service for <u>topsoil Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring</u>. Until now, with the support of WP2, the user requirements have been identified and prioritised. Challenges and issues have been highlighted and related to <u>defining a service logic that can support CAP Strategy plans and the needed accuracy</u>.</p> <p>The next step, and after the development of the platform, the delivery of the data products and the deployment of the first version of the services, is to test the service, its accuracy, define the service logic and provide feedback to data, platform and services providers for improvements and the performance of the services.</p>		
<i>Service</i>	<i>Data Provider</i>	<i>Service Provider</i>
Topsoil Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring	EV ILVO, LV	EVI ILVO with the support of AgroApps

Table 1. Short description of the Flemish Business Cases, considering customer requirements.

<i>Lithuania Business Case: Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP</i>		
<i>Business Customer: NPA</i>		
<i>Type of organisation: Paying Agency (PA)</i>		
<i>Data products and service providers: NOA</i>		

Short description: Lithuanian business case focuses on deploying ENVISION services to monitor crop type, vegetation status, grassland mowing/ploughing, soil erosion. They are also interested in other services for monitoring organic farming requirements and SOC if cost-effective and less time-consuming.

Until now, with the support of WP2, the user requirements have been identified and prioritised. Additionally, issues have been highlighted as the map accuracy (compared to in-situ data), the availability of outputs in a particular period, or whether they will mask layers of interest with information from outcomes (important for controller to link multiple requirements).

Next step, and after the development of the platform, the delivery of the data products and the deployment of the first version of the services is to test the services and provide feedback to platform developers (Draxis) and services providers (NOA) for improvements and the performance of the services.

<i>Service</i>	<i>Data Provider</i>	<i>Service Provider</i>
Crop Type	NPA	NOA
Vegetation status	NPA	NOA
Grassland mowing/ploughing	NPA	NOA
Soil erosion	NPA	NOA

Table 2. Short description of the Lithuanian Business Cases, considering customers requirements.

Cyprus Business Case: Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP

Customer: **CAPO**

Type of organisation: Paying Agency (PA)

Data products and service providers: **NOA**

Short description: Cypriot business case focuses on employing ENVISION services to monitor crop type, vegetation status, In addition they are also interested in other services like crop growth (organic and non-organic identification).

Until now, with the support of WP2, the user requirements have been identified and prioritised. Additionally, issues have been highlighted as for example, how important it for them is to receive information about the cultivation of specific crop types even in very small parcels within a small frequency of time (e.g., to distinguish Winter and Spring potatoes), identify and distinguish organic and conventional crop and to be able to monitor pesticide use on the declared plots. CAPO also emphasises on the need to receive ENVISION outputs more frequently throughout the entire application period to be able to help and explain to applicants about possible implications of wrong declarations for multiple agri-environmental schemes and furthermore, CAPO would like to be able to detect new farming activity in designated Natura areas, distinguish burnt areas between random wildfires and intentional burning (usually straw) and by utilising proximity tools to identify excess nitrogen fertilisation close to waterways, rivers and ponds.

Next step, and after the development of the platform, the delivery of the data products and the deployment of the first version of the services is to test the services and provide feedback to platform developers (Draxis) and services providers (NOA) for improvements and the performance of the services.

<i>Service</i>	<i>Data Provider</i>	<i>Service Provider</i>
Crop Type	CAPO	NOA
Vegetation status	CAPO	NOA

Table 3. Short description of the Cypriot BC, considering customers requirements.

Serbian Business Case: Monitoring organic farming requirements

Customers: **OCS**

Type of organisation: Certification Body (CB)

Data products and service providers: **Aggroapps**

Short description: Serbian business case focuses on employing ENVISION services that allow **organic farming monitoring**. The business case demonstrates how EO technology uptake can improve the overall monitoring of organic certification requirements such as farmland expansion, biodiversity, GHG emissions, water and soil.

Until now, with the support of WP2, the user requirements have been identified and prioritised. Preferences have been highlighted, for example, to identify crop type data on conventional plots of the same operators that are involved in organic farming once a year, to track reductions in the number of plants several times a year and to receive Envision outputs and information on yields of each crop per parcel and also yearly identify crops in neighbouring non-organic plots.

Next step, and after the development of the platform, the delivery of the data products and the deployment of the first version of the services is to test the services and provide feedback to platform developers (Draxis) and services providers (Aggroapps) for improvements and the performance of the services. Additionally, InoSens (i.e., an Agtech Consultancy Company) will create the overall infrastructure and framework of this business case.

Service	Data Provider	Service Provider
Crop growth (organic and non-organic identification)	OCS	AgroApps

Table 4. Short description of the Serbian Business Cases, considering customers' requirements.

The UK Business case will be created in accordance with the details that will be finalised with LEAF in the coming days.

1.3 WP5 Tasks

To achieve the objectives of WP5, 4 tasks have been determined

Task Number	Task Name	Task Leader & Contributors	Short Description
T.5.1	Business cases planning	EV ILVO NPA, LV, CAPO, OCS, INOS	This task aims to provide <u>guidelines and action plans</u> for each of the business cases to be deployed and validated using the ENVISION products and services.
T. 5.2	Business cases implementation	EV ILVO DRXS, NOA, NPA, LV, CAPO, OCS, INOS, AgroApps	This task will carry out the necessary activities to facilitate the <u>implementation and monitoring of the performance of the business cases and support the Lighthouse Customers to decide which ENVISION data products they are interested in and determine their level and type of involvement the project.</u>

T.5.3	Business cases evaluation	EV ILVO NPA, LV, CAPO, OCS, INOS	This task aims to evaluate <u>each business case</u> individually.
T.5.4	Add-on development showcase and capacity building	ITC DRXS, AgroApps INOS,	This task aims to increase the capacity of companies and organisations that offer commercial products and develop new and improved products and services by building upon the ENVISION solution.

Table 5. Short Description of the Tasks

1.4 Deliverables

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Task No:	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Deadline
D5.1	Implementation Guidelines	T5.1	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M16 DEC21
D5.2	Business cases action plan	T5.1	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M18 FEB22
D5.3	Evaluation criteria	T5.2	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M22 JUN22
D5.4	Intermediate business case implementation report	T5.2	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M26 OCT22
D5.5	Intermediate report on the evaluation of services	T5.3	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M26 OCT22
D5.6	Final business case implementation report	T5.3	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M34 JUN23
D5.7	Final report on the evaluation of services	T5.3	EV ILVO	Report	Public	M34 JUN23
D5.8	Add-on development showcase & capacity building report	T5.4	DRXS	Report	Public	M34 JUN23

Table 6. List of deadlines for WP5

1.5 Implementation and evaluation of business cases

Following the D5.1 Implementation Guidelines (BIG), to ensure successful implementation and monitoring progress for all BC, WP5 will provide a D5.2 BC Action Plan (BAP). The business case Action Plan will provide a detailed work plan focusing on the timely execution of each business case.

The business case action plans define details of operation such as Involved partners with their roles and their specific activities as those defined in D5.1, timely execution of each task and activities, calendar of performance evaluation and feedback reporting, directions for “plan B” solutions.

In line with the action plan, business case implementation reports will be developed as a way of monitoring the performance of each business case, and they will be delivered at two stages: An intermediate report in M26 (D5.4), and a final report in M34 (D5.6).

For the evaluation of each BC individually, the evaluation criteria will be defined together with the BC actors as part of deliverable **D5.3 Evaluation criteria**. The established criteria will focus on assessing the:

- Performance,
- Usability,
- Effectiveness,
- User acceptance,
- Adoption,

of the ENVISION products and services and their **economic, environmental, and societal impact**.

The evaluation process will go in parallel with the implementation process. Questionnaires, interviews, and regular meetings with the project participants will be used as ways to collect and rate.

Monitoring the envisaged business cases milestones, and evaluation report will be delivered at two stage: An Intermediate report on the evaluation of services in M 26 (D5.5) and Final report on the evaluation of services in M34 (D5.7)

1.6 Alignment with capacity-building activities

ENVISION will undertake several activities, including the realisation of showcases, workshops and webinars, and the hosting of a hackathon on solutions and applications that can leverage the ENVISION data and services into valuable input/tools.

A contest (Hackathon) will be organised by DRXS, ITC and INOS, undertaking the technical training of all participants, so they are provided with the necessary knowledge and guidance on how to access the ENVISION data and services and how to use them in their implementations. Moreover, business modelling is supported through the CANVAS methodology.

Task 5.1 and 5.2 activities and especially the action plans will consider and support capacity building activities reminding the additional partner's responsibility to report through JotForms about any external communication at the designated place.

2 Role descriptions and activities

2.1 Actors of the WP5

The list of WP5 actors will be updated frequently to include any updates related to the Lighthouse Customers.

No	Name (Short name)	Participation in Tasks and Business Cases
1	DRAXIS Environmental (DRXS)	Participate in the planning and implementation phase of the Business case and contribute to Task 5.4 Add-on development showcase and capacity building.
2	National Observatory of Athens (NOA)	Participate in the planning and implementation phase of the Lithuanian and Cypriot Business case.
3	National Paying Agency (NPA)	Responsible for the Lithuanian business case (Monitoring multiple environmental and climate requirements of CAP)
4	Flemish Department of Agriculture and Fisheries (LV)	Responsible for the Belgium Business Case (Monitoring the condition of the soil)
5	Organismos Agrotikon Pliromon (CAPO)	Responsible for the Cypriot Business Case (Monitoring multiple environmental and climate requirements of CAP)
6	Doo Organic Control System Subotica (OCS)	Responsible for the Serbian Business Case (Monitoring organic farming practices)
7	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw – En Visserijonderzoek (EV ILVO),	WP Leader and Task Leader in 5.1-5.2 and 5.3.
10	ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster Murska Sobota (ITC)	Leader of Task 5.4 Add-on development showcase and capacity building.
12	INOSSENS Doo Novi Sad (INOS)	Participate in the planning, implementation, and evaluation phase of the Serbian and UK (LEAF) Business case and contribute to the Add-on development showcase and capacity building.
13	AgroApps I.K.E (AgroApps),	Participate in the planning, implementation, and evaluation phase of the Serbian Business

No	Name (Short name)	Participation in Tasks and Business Cases
		case and contribute to the Task 5.4 Add-on development showcase and capacity building.
14	Linking Environment And Farming (LEAF)	Responsible for the UK business case focusing on LEAF Marque Certification and how EO data could be used to improve the accreditation process.

Table 7. Actors of the WP5

2.2 Role descriptions

In this section, we are providing the Role Name and a short description of the role.

Role ID	Role Name	Role Short Description (underline verbs highlight the major activities)
R1	Work Package Leader (WPL)	<u>Responsible for managing</u> the WP activities and <u>supporting</u> the implementation of the Business Cases. WPL also <u>defines</u> the Business Cases, <u>assigns roles</u> and <u>supports the evaluation</u> of the ENVISION data products and services. They <u>collaborate</u> closely with the Facilitators and the WP partners.
R2	Business case Facilitator (BCF)	<u>Facilitates</u> Business Use Cases, <u>supporting</u> efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users. Depending on the complexity of a business case, a Facilitator can act as a Consumer or as End Users or a Data Provider.
R3	Product & Service Consumers (PSC)	<u>A PSC can actively participate in the co-production</u> of the ENVISION products and services, <u>test them</u> under various conditions and <u>validate</u> them within the Business Cases. A PSC can <u>participate</u> in one or many Business Cases. A PSC also <u>integrates</u> , if needed, the services into their line of business as a way to <u>develop</u> the business flow. A PSC may also act as an end-user when the end-users are actors within the same organisation. A PSC also acts as the primary BC Evaluator.

Role ID	Role Name	Role Short Description (underline verbs highlight the major activities)
R4	Service Provider (SP)	An <u>SP develops</u> and <u>delivers</u> services for the implementation of the Business Cases. They also <u>improve</u> the services using feedback coming from the Consumers and the End Users.
R5	Platform Provider (PP)	A <u>PP develops</u> and <u>delivers</u> the Envision Platform and its tools by using suitable techniques and technologies. The SP delivers their services through the Envision Platform. The PP <u>updates</u> the platform using the collected feedback from the Consumers, End Users and the Data and Service Providers.
R6	Data Provider (DP)	DPs <u>identify</u> , <u>collect</u> , <u>integrate</u> , and <u>validate</u> all available ancillary data sets to feed ENVISION's products and services. Service Providers use the data resources that come from the Data Providers to deliver their services.
R7	End Users (EnU)	EnUs ultimately <u>use the service</u> (or the product) within a Business Case, for example, the Farmers or Agronomists. An EnU also acts as the primary BC Evaluator.
R7	BC Evaluators (BCE)	BCEs <u>evaluate</u> the business cases and their added value. This role is performed mainly by the Consumers and the End Users; however, providers may participate as evaluators <u>providing</u> their feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.

Table 8. Role descriptions

2.3 Activities

In this section, we list the activities providing more details. We have also included activities related to the reporting, monitoring and management of each Business Case.

Activities ID	Activities
A1	<u>Managing</u> the WP activities
A2	<u>Supporting</u> the implementation of the Business Cases by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.
A3	<u>Defining</u> the Business Cases.
A4	<u>Assigning roles</u> to the Business Cases.
A5	<u>Supporting the evaluation</u> of the ENVISION data products and services.
A6	<u>Collaborating</u> closely with the Facilitators and the WP partners.
A7	<u>Facilitating</u> Business Use Cases.
A8	<u>Supporting</u> efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.
A9	<u>Co-producing</u> the ENVISION products and services within the Business Cases
A10	<u>Testing</u> under various conditions the ENVISION products and services within the Business Cases.
A11	<u>Validating</u> the ENVISION products and services within the Business Cases.
A12	<u>Integrating</u> , if needed, the services into his line of business.
A13	<u>Developing</u> the business flow (or business logic) within the Business Cases
A14	<u>Developing</u> services for the implementation of the Business Cases.
A15	<u>Delivering</u> the services for the implementation of the Business Cases through the Envision Platform
A16	<u>Improving</u> the services using feedback coming from the Consumers and the End Users.
A17	<u>Developing</u> the Envision Platform and its tools by using suitable techniques and technologies.
A18	<u>Delivering</u> the Envision Platform and its tools to providers, consumers, and end-users using suitable techniques, infrastructures and technologies.

A19	<u>Updating</u> the platform using the collected feedback from the Consumers, End Users and the Data and Service Providers.
A20	<u>Identifying</u> all available ancillary data sets to feed ENVISION products and services.
A21	<u>Collecting</u> all available ancillary data sets to feed ENVISION products and services.
A22	<u>Integrating</u> all available ancillary data sets to feed ENVISION products and services.
A23	<u>Validating</u> all available ancillary data sets to feed ENVISION products and services.
A24	<u>Using the service</u> (or the product) within a Business Case.
A25	<u>Evaluating</u> the business cases and their added value and
A26	<u>Providing</u> feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.
A27	<u>Organizing</u> and chairing meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.
A28	<u>Participating</u> in the BC level meetings.
A29	<u>Monitoring</u> the Business Cases progress and assigned activities in the BC guidelines.
A30	<u>Executing</u> Business Cases activities as defined in the Action Plans (BC AP) within a defined duration.
A31	<u>Reporting</u> on the Business Cases progress using the official reported tools as those provided by the WP leader.
A32	<u>Creating</u> extra sub-roles and sub-activities for BC implementation progress if needed.
A33	<u>Managing and organizing</u> the internal organizational resources.
A34	<u>Organizing</u> internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.
A35	<u>Participating</u> and/or providing input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys.

Table 9. Activities

2.4 Activities and assignments to roles

Activities ID	R1 WPL	R2 BCF	R3 PSC	R4 SP	R5 PP	R6 DP	R7 EnU	R8 BCE
A1	✓							
A2	✓			✓				
A3	✓							
A4	✓							
A5	✓							
A6	✓							
A7		✓						
A8		✓						
A9			✓					
A10			✓					
A11			✓					
A12			✓					
A13			✓					
A14				✓				
A15				✓				
A16				✓				
A17					✓			
A18					✓			
A19					✓			
A20						✓		
A21						✓		
A22						✓		
A23						✓		
A24							✓	
A25								✓
A26								✓
A27	✓	✓						
A28	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
A29	✓	✓						
A30	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
A31		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
A32	✓							
A33	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
A34	✓							
A35	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

(✓: Main responsibility, ✓: Participate and/or Provide support)

Table 10. Activities and assignments to roles

3 Collaboration, communication and monitoring tools

3.1 Communication channels

Considering the international level of the project and the number of different partners, it is necessary to make the best of web tools. To ease the exchange of information and documents among partners, the project has decided to make use of different tools:

- **File storage.**

Any material produced during the BC implementation and evaluation processes must be stored to the collaborative file repository **folder structure under the WP5 sub site**. Each Business Case actor will have access only to their data (access control). This gives all members direct and secure access to the latest updates and facilitates data exchange between WPs and BCs.

The Lighthouse customers will have access only to their Business Case folder.

- **E-mail communication**

For direct, daily and frequent communication, email correspondence is highly supported. For this purpose, different email groups will be created and a table with BC actor's contacts information has been created. This table can be found on share Folder at Dropbox.

- **Platforms for online meetings**

Different platforms will be used as an alternative for physical meetings, such as: Google meeting, Microsoft Teams, Skype etc. The coordination and set-up of online meetings can be done through the use of doodles.

- **Physical meetings**

Although they offer more robust communication and collaboration opportunities, the wide distribution of consortium members and potential customers (LHC) across Europe and the current Covid-19 situation may lead to limitations of physical meetings.

- **Visual Collaboration**

We will use Mural as a visual collaboration environment to support visual collaboration during the elicitation process.

3.2 Management of the meetings and workshops

For adequate collaboration, proper meeting management is a necessity. WP5 has defined two meeting levels, particularly relevant for appropriate BC implementation, and in addition, it ensures a multi-actor approach and supports the project monitoring and accountability.

Meetings are used to:

- discuss and address relevant topics of the BC execution,
- follow the progress of implementation,
- exchange of information among all the partners,
- collaborate between WPs, BC actors and related Project partners.

Depending on the meeting level, different attendees are involved with different responsibilities in terms of monitoring. Each attendee has a defined role in ensuring appropriate participation and

preparation of meetings (Table 11 Meeting types). The overview of the meeting's details is given in the below.

Meeting Features	Meeting Level	
	WP Level	BC Level
Meeting participants	WP Leader WP Partners	Facilitator Consumer – End Users Providers (not always needed) Evaluators (in case of LC) WPL
Meeting Agenda & Minutes prepared by	WP Leader	The facilitator (or the WP Leader on exceptional cases)
Use of Meeting Agenda & Minutes templates	Obligatory	Obligatory
Scheduling responsible	WP Leader	Facilitator
Meeting scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening the collaboration between WP and BC actors • Allowing a bottom-up approach to problem-solving. • WPs are constantly updated on the status of the BCs. • Establishing periodical communication between WP and BC actors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easing the coordination of the BC. • Ensuring the follow-up of the activities. • Allowing the Facilitator to solve possible problems on time • Ensuring constant evaluation for each BC. • Establishing collaboration between BC Actors. • Establishing periodical communication between BC actors within the assigned BC.

Table 11 Meeting types

3.3 Monitoring and documentation guidelines

The project needs to establish strict, but effective procedures for monitoring and evaluation of BCs.

- For BC monitoring purposes

Every BC needs to report back to the WPL and follow the milestones indicated in their **Action Plan** when it comes to progress monitoring. As previously described, the BCF is responsible for delivering indicated reports and milestones on time, using the templates that provided by the WPL.

These reports will be the critical and needed inputs for WP5 deliverables (D5.4, D5.5, D5.6, D5.7). They will help WPL and other partners to support BC implementation by indicating improvements if needed.

To accomplish uniformity, formality, consistency, and transparency, WP5 team have prepared and collected several documents to ease the implementation of the guidelines. The documents prepared are:

- BC actors contact list.
- Template for the agenda and minute of the meetings.
- A table containing all the deadlines for the deliverables of WP5 (Table 6).

All the official documents produced during the BC implementation and evaluation progress should use the template provided by the WPL. Documentation should be prepared according to the directions given by the Project Coordinator.

The way files are organized and assigned names have a significant impact on the traceability of those files and the ability to determine their contents subsequently. File names should be allocated consistently and given a descriptive name so it will be clear where and what to find in specific files.

Accordingly, files and working documents naming should follow the naming convention described below:

- Use “_” instead of space
- Document related to BC should start with “BC_document name-date”

(e.g. BC_2_agenda_YYYY_MM_DD.docx)

- Document related to WP should start with “WP_document name-date”

(e.g. WP_minutes_YYYY_MM_DD.docx)

- if the document is modified it should contain a version number and the date of last modification

(e.g. V2_BC_2_minutes_YYYY_MM_DD.docx)

WP Leader will ensure that the relevant and the most updated version of the document is uploaded on Dropbox.

3.4 Risk and mitigation measures

The main **risks** that were identified for BC implementation and evaluation process are summarised in the table below.

Risk	Impact	Short Explanation
Difficulties in the establishment of an effective communication ladder with the business cases actors	Medium	<p>Task 5.1 officially started on M9, however and also due to Covid restrictions, it is difficult to establish the needed communication level with all actors. As a mitigation measure we decide to participate to WP2 and WP4 activities as a way to understand and map in advance the business case actors, relations, needs, priorities and specific requirements. Also to familiarize.</p> <p>And we have created an effective cooperation and communication framework within the Guideline to deal with the difficulties that the Covid restrictions may cause in the coming days.</p>
Insufficient (unbalance) support of the commercialization and dissemination activities.	Medium	We need to align our effort to support equally the deployment, feedback collection, evaluation (the iterations) and commercialization and dissemination activities. WP5 creates strong links with the relative WPs, providing feedback coming from the implementation and evaluation process
The participation of farmers as data providers in the business cases is low.	Low	All farmers will be engaged through their respective PAs and CBs, and there will be extensive dissemination activities, carefully designed in order to clearly present the benefits of ENVISION in the long-term (amelioration of monitoring procedure) and in the short-term (free agricultural consulting).
In situ data for model validation.	Medium	We have created the necessary monitoring framework within the guidelines to identify and respond quickly to potential problems.
Delays in Feedback to other WPs	Low	Apart from the intermediary reports, WP leader will be in close collaboration with the WP2, WP3, WP4 leaders to deliver end-user feedback on time and discuss emerging issues, during or parallel of the monthly meetings.

<p>Development and monitoring of new Business cases coming from Lighthouse customers</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>The structure and the logic of the guidelines and the action plan has been designed to deliver flexibility and capacity to manage more than 4 BCs simultaneously. Additionally, WP5 leader is from the beginning of the project in close collaboration with all WP leaders and the coordinator participating in all relative activities, either those concern the lighthouse engagement or the definition of the requirement or the meetings with the service and platform providers.</p>
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Table 12 Risk assessment and mitigation actions

4 Business cases actors and their role (Mapping)

In this section, we will present per Business Case the actors and their assigned roles. We will also explain how we will manage the LC and develop new business cases.

4.1 Matrixes of responsibilities

<i>Flemish Business Case: Monitoring the condition of the soil</i>								
Business case Actors	Business Case Role							
	R1 WPL	R2 BCF	R3 PSC	R4 SP	R5 PP	R6 DP	R7 EnU	R8 BCE
LV		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
DRXS					✓			✓
EV ILVO	✓			✓		✓		✓
AgroApps				✓				✓
Farmers							✓	✓

(✓: Main responsibility, ✓: Participate and/or Provide support)

Table 13. Business Cases 1 Actors And Their Role

<i>Lithuania Business Case: Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP</i>								
Business case Actors	Business Case Role							
	R1 WPL	R2 BCF	R3 PSC	R4 SP	R5 PP	R6 DP	R7 EnU	R8 BCE
EV ILVO	✓							
NPA		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
DRXS					✓			✓
NOA				✓				✓
Farmers							✓	✓

(✓: Main responsibility, ✓: Participate and/or Provide support)

Table 14. Business Cases 2 Actors And Their Role

Cyprus Business Case: Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP								
Business case Actors	Business Case Role							
	R1 WPL	R2 BCF	R3 PSC	R4 SP	R5 PP	R6 DP	R7 EnU	R8 BCE
EV ILVO	✓							
CAPO		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
DRXS					✓			✓
NOA				✓				✓
Farmers							✓	✓

(✓: Main responsibility, ✓: Participate and/or Provide support)

Table 15. Business Cases 3. Actors And Their Role

Serbian Business Case: Monitoring organic farming requirements								
Business case Actors	Business Case Role							
	R1 WPL	R2 BCF	R3 PSC	R4 SP	R5 PP	R6 DP	R7 EnU	R8 BCE
EV ILVO	✓							
OCS		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
DRXX					✓			✓
AgroApps				✓				✓
INOSENSE						✓		✓
Farmers							✓	✓

(✓: Main responsibility, ✓: Participate and/or Provide support)

Table 16. Business Cases 4. Actors And Their Role

4.2 Lighthouse customers and our approach

Lighthouse Customers have the option to choose the level and type of their involvement in the project during ENVISION's implementation and evaluation phases. Depending on their specific needs, each Lighthouse Customer will decide which ENVISION products and services they are interested in.

All Lighthouse Customers that are willing to participate in BC implementation and evaluation processes will act as BC Evaluators. They will contribute to further enhancing the results of the ENVISION project by providing extra information and feedback for the evaluation of Envision products and services through the workshops and demonstration events that will be provided.

Besides acting as a BC evaluator, they can also choose to participate in small-scale testing and evaluation of ENVISION's services by applying their chosen ENVISION services on their own data and small-scale testing area. This will create a new BC and according to that, the roles, responsibilities and assigned activities in the BC guideline will be integrated for each Lighthouse Customer Business Cases.

5 CONCLUSIONS: the contribution of this deliverable

The BC guideline is the starting point of the work that will be performed under WP5 (BC implementation and evaluation). The guideline is designed to be the reference point for the BC actors during the BC implementation and evaluation processes, as it provides information about the actor roles and assigned activities, information for monitoring procedures, specifics on meeting management and its participants, as well as the documentation criteria and communication protocols between the different business cases actors.

The overall guidelines and information provided throughout the deliverable will ensure:

- Smooth and uniform implementation across the business cases.
- Smooth progress through a multi-actor approach by enhancing the close cooperation and communication between WPs, BC Facilitators, BC actors.
- A bottom-up approach to problem-solving, which will ensure speedy responses to possible problems.

Additionally, being a concrete base for the BC Action plan will facilitate the actions that will take place during the execution of BC action plans.

6 ANNEX

6.1 Template for meeting minutes

Meeting Name:			
Meeting called by:	<i>BC Facilitator / WP Leader</i>		
No. of attendees			
Date of Meeting:		Time:	
Minutes Prepared By:	<i>BC Facilitator / WP Leader</i>	Place:	<i>(Google meeting, Microsoft teams, Skype , Physical Meeting, etc.)</i>
1. Meeting Objective			
2. Attendance at Meeting			
Name and surname		Organization name	
3. Agenda			
Discussion			
Conclusions & Decided Action			
5. Next Meeting			

6.2 Template for Agenda

Agenda for:			
Date:		Time:	
No. of expected			
Agenda issued by:	<i>Organization name</i>		
	<i>Representative name</i>		
	E-mail:		
Place:	<i>(Google meeting, Microsoft teams, Skype , Physical Meeting, etc.)</i>		
Link:	<i>Add</i>		
LIST OF PARTICIPANTS			
Name and surname	Organization name		
WORKING SESSION (OR DISCUSSION)			
<i>Day, DD/MM/YYYY</i>			
Time	Topic	Presenter	
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION			

6.3 BC actors contact list

Business Case 1 : Monitoring the condition of the soil Customers: LV Country:Flanders				
Country	Organization	Role	Main Contact Person(s)	email
GR	DRXS	PP	Panagiota Syropoulou	syropoulou.p@draxis.gr
BE	LV	BCF, PSC, EnU	Sebastiaan Philips	sebastiaan.philips@lv.vlaanderen.be
BE	EV ILVO	SP, WPL	Panos Ilias Tuna Coppens	Panos.Ilias@ilvo.vlaanderen.be Tuna.Coppens@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
GR	AgroApps		Ifigeneia Tsioutsia	iftsioutsia@agroapps.gr
Business Case 2: Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP Customers: NPA Country: Lithuania				
Country	Organization	Role	Main Contact Person(s)	email
GR	DRXS	PP	Panagiota Syropoulou	syropoulou.p@draxis.gr
GR	NOA	SP	Mariza Kaskara Vassilis Sitokonstantinou Jason Tsardanidis Thanasis Drivas	kaskara@noa.gr vsito@noa.gr j.tsardanidis@noa.gr tdrivas@noa.gr
LT	NPA	BCF, PSC, EnU	Aušrius Kučinskas Martynas Rimgaila Kristina Jarmalavičienė Salomėja Rybokienė	Ausrius.Kucinskas@nma.lt Martynas.Rimgaila@nma.lt Kristina.Jarmalaviciene@nma.lt Salomeja.Rybokiene@nma.lt
BE	EV ILVO	WPL	Panos Ilias Tuna Coppens	Panos.Ilias@ilvo.vlaanderen.be Tuna.Coppens@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
Business Case 3: Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP Customers: CAPO Country: Cyprus				
Country	Organization	Role	Main Contact Person(s)	email
GR	DRXS	PP	Panagiota Syropoulou	syropoulou.p@draxis.gr
GR	NOA	SP	Mariza Kaskara Vassilis Sitokonstantinou Jason Tsardanidis Thanasis Drivas	kaskara@noa.gr vsito@noa.gr j.tsardanidis@noa.gr tdrivas@noa.gr
CY	CAPO	BCF, PSC, EnU	George Groutas George Farkonis	ggroutas@capo.gov.cy gfarkonis@capo.gov.cy
BE	EV ILVO	WPL	Panos Ilias Tuna Coppens	Panos.Ilias@ilvo.vlaanderen.be Tuna.Coppens@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
Business Case 4: Monitoring organic farming requirements Customers: OCS Country: Serbia				
Country	Organization	Role	Main Contact Person(s)	email
GR	DRXS	PP	Panagiota Syropoulou	syropoulou.p@draxis.gr

RS	OCS	BCF, PSC, EnU	Kosta Novaković Bojana Vignjević Svetlana Vitomirović	project@organica.rs
BE	EV ILVO	WPL	Panos Ilias Tuna Coppens	Panos.Ilias@ilvo.vlaanderen.be Tuna.Coppens@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
GR	AgroApps	SP	Ifigeneia Tsioutsia	iftsioutsia@agroapps.gr
RS	INOS		Nemanja Nićin Vladimir Mrkajić	nicin@inosens.rs mrkajic@inosens.rs

Business Case 5: UK Business Case

Customers: LEAF Country: UK

Country	Organization	Role	Main Contact Person(s)	email
GR	AgroApps	PP	Ifigeneia Tsioutsia	iftsioutsia@agroapps.gr
UK	LEAF	BCF, PSC	Nigel Evans	Nigel.Evans@leaf.eco
BE	EV ILVO	WPL	Panos Ilias Tuna Coppens	Panos.Ilias@ilvo.vlaanderen.be Tuna.Coppens@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
RS	INOS		Nemanja Nićin Vladimir Mrkajić	nicin@inosens.rs mrkajic@inosens.rs

End of Document

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